

A Machine Learning Approach for Reliable Object Tracking

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Abstract. Object tracking is a critical task that finds its applications in various fields including surveillance and autonomous robots. However, most of the work on object tracking has been developed on images and video data. In contrast, the aim of our work is to develop reliable object tracking system based on sequence of measurements which can be obtained from radio sensors, that are more suitable for privacy-concerned applications. In addition, we propose to use linear regression, in contrast to complex data-driven models, to demonstrate its performance against conventional tracking algorithm i.e., particle filter. Our experimental results show that LR can predict a moving object's position with minimal error and significantly outperforms the particle filter by more than 90%. All the experiments have been validated via simulations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Linear regression, Machine Learning, Object tracking.

1 Introduction

Object tracking plays a crucial role in various fields and applications. It enables the real-time monitoring and analysis of moving objects, providing valuable insights and facilitating decision-making processes. In the field of computer vision [1], object tracking is essential for tasks such as video surveillance, autonomous navigation, human-computer interaction, and augmented reality. However, computer vision methods are often susceptible to adversarial attacks [2-5]. Apart from that, object tracking also finds applications in robotics and specifically in vision and radio based simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [6], where tracking objects allows robots to interact with their environment, perform manipulation tasks, and navigate safely. Object tracking is also utilized in sports analysis, medical imaging, traffic monitoring, and many other domains. By accurately tracking objects, it enables us to understand their behavior, predict their future positions, and extract meaningful information from dynamic scenes,

With the advancements in computer vision, vision-based sensors have gained an advantage over other sensors. Therefore, most of the literature on object tracking focuses on detecting and tracking objects in images or video sequences. In contrast to the Kalman filter, which is designed for linear systems and Gaussian posterior distributions, the particle filter excels in solving nonlinear problems and handling multimodal posterior distributions. The particle filter is a widely adopted algorithm used in various applications for object tracking. It is commonly employed for tracking objects in both radar data and camera-based data. For example, in a study [7], a particle filter algorithm was implemented to detect the number of objects and track them in various image sequences. Another study [8] proposed a combination of a particle filter and a correlation filter to track moving objects in images. Additionally, besides using image sequences for object tracking, many studies have utilized LiDAR data for object tracking [9].

In the context of radio-based detection and tracking using mm-wave signals, the work presented in [10] has developed Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture (PMBM) filters based on particle filters to detect and track vehicles in a 5G wireless network scenario. Another study employed a particle filter and probability hypothesis density filter to implement SLAM for vehicle positioning and mapping in a 5G network [11].

With the advent of artificial intelligence, plethora of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models have been developed to solve the problem of object tracking. However, most of the studies in the recent literature have employed ML and DL models to track objects from sequence of images or videos.[12-15] In contrast, the objective of our work is to track a moving object with the help of measurements (i.e., position estimates) obtained from a wireless sensor. Unlike cameras, wireless sensors can ensure privacy and works better in low-light conditions. Although a study [16] in have utilized measurements to track multiple moving targets, however, they proposed a complex DL architecture i.e., Transformer, to achieve the goal. In contrast, the goal of our work is to leverage the power of a less computationally expensive ML model and compare it with the commonly used conventional method i.e., particle filter. Our work demonstrates that while the ML model requires some training data, unlike particle filter, it does not need to have a prior knowledge of the target's motion model, nor does it require a known reference object in the environment to perform the object tracking. The rest of the paper is categorized as follows. Methodology is explained in Section 2. Section 3 describes the experimental setup and the obtained results, whereas conclusions along with future directions are discussed in Section 4.

2 Methodology

Below we describe the conventional and our proposed methods for object tracking in detail.

2.1 Particle Filter

Particle filters are extensively employed to estimate and track the positions of moving objects. Particles serve as estimates or approximations of the desired target's position. The implementation of a particle filter involves the following steps:

Initialization The initial step involves generating a large number of particles ($N=1000$) uniformly across the space of interest. Each particle represents a potential estimate of the target's position within that space.

Weighting This step involves assigning importance weights to each particle based on the proximity of its measurement to the target's measurements. The nature of the measurement depends on the specific application. To implement this step, a reference object with a known position is required. This object is utilized to compare measurements between the target and the particles. For instance, let's consider the scenario of localizing a moving target. In this case, a tag with a predetermined position serves as the reference. The target is equipped with a sensor that measures the distance between itself and the tag. However, these sensor measurements can be noisy and may not accurately represent the true distance between the target and the tag. At each time-step, the sensor on the target acquires a measurement of the tag's range. Simultaneously, the distance between each particle and the tag is computed. The next step involves calculating the error by comparing the sensor's measurements with the particles' measurements of the tag. To assign weights to the particles, a Gaussian distribution is employed. The weight assignment process is as follows:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

In the equation, μ represents the error between the target's measurement and the particle's measurement of the tag, while x is set to 0. The term $(x - \mu)$ captures the variation in the particle's position relative to the target. The parameter σ governs the standard deviation of the distribution. A higher value of σ indicates noisier sensor measurements, leading to higher weights assigned to particles that are farther from the target's measured position. Conversely, a lower σ indicates greater confidence in the sensor measurements, resulting in lower weights assigned to particles that deviate significantly from the target's measured position. Therefore, σ serves as a tunable parameter that should be assigned based on the level of noise present in the sensor's measurements.

Resampling In this step, the particles are resampled based on the weights assigned to each particle. Particles with higher weights have a greater likelihood of being resampled. The resampling process consists of the following steps:

- Select a random index (i) from the set of N particles.
- Determine the maximum weight from the list of particles' weights.
- For each particle, generate a random number called Beta and compare it to the weight of the i^{th} particle. If Beta is greater than the weight of the i^{th} particle, subtract the weight from Beta and update the index accordingly. Repeat this

process until Beta becomes smaller than the weight of the particle associated with the updated index (i).

- Once Beta is smaller than the weight of the particle at index (i), collect or resample the particles corresponding to that index from the total list of particles.
- Repeat the resampling process N times, ensuring that after the resampling, we still have N particles. However, particles with higher weights are more likely to be repeated in the list of resampled particles.

Fuzzing Once the particles have been resampled, the next step involves perturbing the particles by introducing noise. This process, known as fuzzing, adds some level of noise to the states of the particles. Fuzzing is essential to prevent the particle filter from repeatedly resampling the same particles at each time-step. By introducing noise, the particles are able to explore a wider range of possible states and avoid convergence to a single solution.

Move The resampled particles are then advanced by one time-step, taking into account the motion model. In other words, the states of the particles are updated based on the specific motion model used. It is crucial to possess prior knowledge of the target's motion model, as it serves as the basis for defining the motion model of the particles. By updating the particle states in accordance with the motion model, the particle filter is able to simulate the movement and trajectory of the target accurately.

Aggregate In the final step, the resampled particles, after undergoing fuzzing and motion updates, are aggregated to obtain the estimate of the target's state at time-step 't'. This aggregation process involves computing the average of the states of the resampled particles. By averaging the states of the particles, the particle filter provides an estimate that represents the collective information gathered from the resampled particles. This estimate serves as the best approximation of the target's state at the given time-step.

Note that the above-mentioned steps are performed for every single time-step and provide the estimate of the target's state at that time-step. Also, the particle filter may need to iterate through multiple time steps before converging to the closest estimate of the target's true location.

2.2 Proposed Methodology

Our proposed methodology aims to leverage a less computationally expensive ML model to achieve better performance for object tracking based on measurements sequence.

Linear Regression ML based linear regression (LR) is a supervised learning algorithm used for predicting continuous numeric values based on a linear relationship between input features and target variables. It seeks to find the best-fitting line that minimizes the difference between predicted and actual values. In simple linear regression, we have

a single input feature denoted as x and a single target variable denoted as y . The equation for simple linear regression is given by:

$$y = mx + c, \quad (2)$$

where y is the target variable (output/predicted value), x is the input feature (input variable), m is the slope of the regression line (also known as the coefficient), and c is the y-intercept (the value of y when $x = 0$). The goal of linear regression is to estimate the values of m and c that best fit the training data.

3 Experiments and Results

The objective of the experiments is to predict the future position of a moving object based on a previous set of measurements. To accomplish this, a dataset of moving objects and their corresponding measurements has been generated using an open-source data generation routine presented in [16]. The process of dataset generation is described below.

3.1 Dataset Generation

To successfully track the position of a moving object using a ML model, a sufficient amount of data is necessary for training the model. Unlike fields such as image processing, computer vision, and natural language processing, where relevant datasets are readily available, there is a lack of datasets that specifically consist of a series of measurements for predicting the next position of moving objects. To overcome this challenge, we make use of an open-source platform, as referenced in [16], which has been developed to generate measurements for random moving objects. We have utilized this routine to generate a dataset of random moving objects and their corresponding series of measurements. Measurements are generated using the motion and measurement model defined in [16]. The state vector of each object consists of 4 states including its position and velocity in 2D i.e., in x and y dimensions. σ controls the motion and measurement noise in the states of each object. Δ_t is the sampling period for acquiring the measurements which is fixed to 0.1. Each instance in the dataset comprises measurements of the x and y positions of a moving object, representing estimates obtained from a sensor. The setup for data generation is explained in [16].

For each moving object, a total of 19 measurements have been recorded over a continuous period of 20 timesteps. The aim is to utilize the 19 previous measurements to predict the position of the object at the 20th time step. By leveraging this dataset, we can train an ML model to learn the patterns and relationships within the measurements, enabling accurate predictions of the object's future position.

Fig. 1. Plots of few data instances from the dataset with varying levels of σ . Each target in the dataset has a different velocity and trajectory associated with it as shown in this figure.

Fig. 1 depicts a subset of the generated data instances for evaluating object tracking. It is important to note that each data instance is independent and distinct from the others. This means that the velocity, positions, and trajectory of the object in each instance vary randomly according to the motion model, as defined in [16].

3.2 Experiments

To evaluate the performance, experiments have been conducted using different levels of noise on the measurement data. Fig. 2 shows the noise-free and noisy data instances, where $\sigma = 0$, and $\sigma = 0.5$, respectively. These figures provide visual examples of the data instances used for assessing the performance of the object-tracking algorithm under various noise conditions. The differences in noise levels allow for the examination of the algorithm's robustness and accuracy in tracking the objects' positions.

To evaluate the performance of the LR model, Fig.2 shows the predictions made by the LR model at time-step 20. These predictions are compared with the corresponding ground truth positions of the objects at that time-step. It is important to note that these figures display the positions of multiple objects from the dataset at the 20th time-step.

Fig. 2. The two figures show the positions of objects from the dataset at time-step = 20. The figures compare the ground truth position and the predicted position from LR. Note that the predicted positions are equal to the ground truth as $\sigma = 0$, hence the predicted positions appear to overlap exactly over the ground truth positions in the left figure. The right figure shows the results obtained over noisy data ($\sigma > 0$), hence the predicted positions show slight variation from the ground truth positions.

In Fig. 2, where the measurements are noise-free ($\sigma = 0$), the predicted positions align precisely with the ground truth positions. Consequently, the predicted positions appear to overlap exactly with the ground truth positions in the figure. This indicates that the LR model accurately predicts the object positions when no measurement noise is present. However, where the measurements have added noise ($\sigma = 0.5$), the predicted positions made by the LR model exhibit slight dispersion from the respective ground truth positions. This dispersion occurs due to the presence of measurement noise, which simulates real-world scenarios with practical levels of noise. Despite the noise, the LR model still provides reasonably accurate predictions, albeit with a slight deviation from the ground truth positions.

For thorough performance analysis, we have evaluated the performance of LR and particle filter using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and standard deviation. MAE computes the difference between the ground truth and the predicted positions of the targets. Mathematically, it is expressed as:

$$MAE(p) = \frac{1}{T_{ot}} \sum_{t=1}^{T_{ot}} |p_t^* - \hat{p}_t|, \quad (3)$$

where $T_{ot} = 100$ represents the number of test examples used for evaluating the MAE. p^* and \hat{p} represent the groundtruth and predicted position from the model, respectively. Eq. (3) can be used to compute the error in both the x and y dimensions of the target's position. On the other hand, the standard deviation is employed to give the robustness of the models' performance used in this experiment. In other words, it tends to depict the consistency of the models' performance over different test examples. In our experiments, standard deviation is computed over the MAE obtained for each example in the test dataset. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$\sigma(p) = \frac{1}{T_{ot}} \sum_{t=1}^{T_{ot}} |\mu(p) - MAE(p_t)|, \quad (4)$$

where $\mu(p)$ represent the MAE computed using Eq. (3), whereas $MAE(p_t)$ represents the error of target's position in t^{th} data instance.

Table 1 shows the performance analysis of LR and particle filter (N = 1000) in terms of the MAE and standard deviation. The metrics have been computed for both the x and y dimensions of the target's position. Furthermore, the performance of our proposed model (LR) is compared with the particle filter evaluated over four different levels of motion and measurement noise controlled by σ . It can be observed from Table 1 that LR achieves the minimum error whereas the particle filter shows large errors around 5m for all noise cases. Although the MAE for LR tends to slightly increase with the increase in σ , as shown in Fig. 3, it still clearly outperforms the particle filter. The errors obtained using the particle filter can be explained by the disparity in the motion models employed in the particle filter and the data instances. The target in each instance of the dataset is independent of the other instances. In other words, each target has a different motion model that defines its velocity and trajectory which is different from targets in other instances. Since the motion model employed in the particle filter differed in terms of velocity from the respective data instance, this variation caused the particle filter to perform poorly, resulting in a large prediction error. Moreover, the standard deviation of the particle filter is also higher as compared to the LR. Again, this trend can be explained by the variation of the motion model between particle filter data instances. On the other hand, LR shows very less standard deviation implying that its performance is consistent over all the test examples.

In summary, what sets LR apart from particle filters is not just the higher prediction accuracy, but the fact that not only it requires any reference object (tag) with the known position in the environment as used in particle filters, also it does not require any prior knowledge regarding the motion model which makes it highly suitable to be employed in unseen environments. Although LR does require some training data to learn the desired function mapping, however, once optimized over the training data, unlike the particle filter, it can perform well over targets with varying transition models.

Table 1. Performance analysis for object tracking in terms of MAE and standard deviation.

Methods	Sigma (σ)	MAE (m)		St.deviation (m)	
		X	Y	X	Y
Particle Filter	0	5.84	6.78	4.41	5.04
	0.3	6.06	6.27	4.97	5.25
	0.5	5.27	5.32	5.05	4.26
	0.7	5.31	4.63	4.88	4.40
Linear Regression	0	$6.26e^{-7}$	$8.55e^{-7}$	$5.06e^{-7}$	$6.06e^{-7}$
	0.3	0.15	0.16	0.12	0.11
	0.5	0.19	0.19	0.14	0.14
	0.7	0.30	0.30	0.23	0.24

Fig. 3. Bar plot comparing the average MAE obtained for the particle filter and LR over test dataset with different levels of noise (σ).

4 Conclusion and Future Directions

In this paper, we addressed the problem of single object tracking based on sensor’s measurement and proposed to employ a simple machine learning algorithm i.e., linear regression to solve it. For this purpose, we leveraged a simulated dataset consisting of x-y measurements recorded for a target with varying velocities and trajectories. In addition we implemented a particle filter and compared its performance with linear regression. Our results show that LR achieves the average prediction error of 0.3m on the noisy data, whereas the particle filter gives the prediction error around 5m. It is evident from the results that the LR has outperformed the conventional particle filter by 93%.

This study is a preliminary step to demonstrate the power of a less computationally expensive machine learning model i.e., LR in accurately tracking a moving object. This study also highlights the challenges of using a specific particle filter for objects with varying transition models. However, this study can be extended in many directions. For instance, particle filters with more complex and non-linear transition models can be employed to evaluate the tracking performance. Similarly, other ML and DL models can be employed to perform object tracking. In addition, this study can be extended from single object to multiple object tracking. Also, the addition of clutter noise in the data and complex object trajectories can reflect more realistic scenarios which can help develop more robust tracking algorithms. Moreover, the experiments can be conducted on real over-the-air data collected by radio sensors [17].

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